

QUALITY ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING SYSTEMS IN THE EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article discusses ideas on improving quality assessment and monitoring. Quality assessment and monitoring systems enable enterprises and organizations to control, analyze, and continuously improve the quality of products or services. These systems are used to identify, analyze, and enhance quality management processes within organizations. Statistical Process Control (SPC) is a statistics-based method used to detect changes in product or service processes and manage them effectively

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Introduction: Based on the Law "On Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a unique national model of education has been established to nurture a physically healthy, morally mature, highly intellectual, and independently thinking generation that looks to the future with confidence. This model is grounded in learner-centered educational technologies, focusing on the needs, interests, talents, and abilities of the students. To cultivate intellectually developed and competitive young people under the principles of continuity and consistency, new state educational standards, qualification requirements, curricula, subject programs, and updated educational resources have been developed and implemented across all levels of education, including higher education specialties and fields.

Assessing the quality of education, conducting its monitoring, and continuously improving the indicators are among the most important priorities today. Ensuring the necessary level of education quality, developing effective methods for education quality management and qualimetry, and forming a methodological approach to these tasks are considered essential goals. In higher education institutions, if the state of education and training quality is objectively assessed using the capabilities of information and communication technologies, negative factors affecting education quality can be corrected in a timely manner,

and forward-looking measures can be implemented. This will help align the quality of education with international standards for training specialists.

Quality assessment and monitoring systems enable enterprises and organizations to control, analyze, and continuously improve the quality of their products or services. These systems ensure that products and services meet customer requirements, enhance competitiveness, and improve overall efficiency. Below, I will provide a detailed explanation of quality assessment and monitoring systems.

Quality Assessment Systems. Quality assessment systems are used to identify, analyze, and improve quality management processes within organizations. These systems are based on international standards or internal benchmarks. Below are some of the most commonly used quality assessment systems:

ISO 9001 Quality Management Standard. ISO 9001 is an international standard for quality management systems, designed to help organizations ensure effective quality management. It focuses on enhancing quality processes and increasing efficiency through the following principles: **Customer Satisfaction:** Delivering products and services that meet customer requirements. **Process Approach:** Identifying, managing, and optimizing internal processes. **Continuous Improvement:** Striving for ongoing enhancements at every stage. **Employee Involvement:** Leveraging the knowledge and experience of employees to improve quality. ISO 9001 standards are widely used globally, enabling organizations to establish quality management systems and meet customer demands effectively.

Six Sigma. Six Sigma is a methodology aimed at reducing errors and achieving high-quality standards through statistical analysis and quality management techniques. It is structured around five key phases: **Define:** Identify and clearly define the problem or specific process. **Measure:** Assess the current state of the process and gather relevant data. **Analyze:** Identify the root causes of issues and conduct a thorough analysis. **Improve:** Implement effective measures to enhance the process. **Control:** Monitor the new system to ensure stability and consistent performance. Six Sigma is widely used in industries to significantly improve the quality of products and services.

Baldrige Award. The **Baldrige Award** is a prestigious recognition in the United States given to organizations that achieve high levels of quality and efficiency. The main objective of this award is to encourage the continuous improvement of quality management systems and motivate organizations to

adopt best practices. Organizations can assess their strengths and weaknesses using the Baldrige criteria, helping them identify areas for improvement and fostering excellence.

These systems and frameworks provide organizations with the tools to control, assess, and continuously improve the quality of their products or services, ensuring they meet customer expectations, increase competitiveness, and enhance efficiency.

EFQM Excellence Model. The **EFQM Excellence Model** was developed by the European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) to enhance quality management systems and improve organizational efficiency. This model is built around several key criteria: **Leadership:** The role of leadership in achieving organizational goals. **Strategy:** Developing clear, long-term strategies. **People:** Engaging employees and enhancing their potential. **Processes:** Optimizing and managing organizational processes. The EFQM model helps organizations enhance process efficiency and meet customer needs effectively, driving overall excellence.

Quality Monitoring Systems. Quality monitoring systems enable organizations to continuously track and analyze the quality of their products or services. Through these systems, organizations can monitor their activities, adapt to changes, and improve quality over time.

KPI (Key Performance Indicators) are essential metrics used to evaluate the success of an organization or process. KPIs help organizations monitor their progress toward objectives and plan actions aligned with their goals. Common KPI categories include: **Financial Indicators:** Profit, expenses, revenue, profitability, etc. **Operational Efficiency:** Ensuring product quality and optimizing production processes. **Customer Satisfaction:** Measuring customer satisfaction levels, feedback, and complaints. Organizations can use KPIs to assess their performance, identify areas for improvement, and implement necessary changes.

The **Balanced Scorecard (BSC)** is a tool used to implement organizational strategies and monitor effectiveness. It is structured around four key perspectives: **Financial Perspective:** Financial performance and profitability metrics. **Customer Perspective:** Meeting customer needs and ensuring satisfaction. **Internal Processes:** Improving the efficiency and quality of internal processes. **Learning and Innovation:** Fostering employee development and introducing innovative approaches. Using the Balanced Scorecard, organizations can track their progress toward long-term strategic goals.

Statistical Process Control (SPC) is a statistics-based method used to identify changes in product or service processes and manage them effectively. The core principles of SPC include: **Data Collection:** Gathering key statistical data on processes. **Charts and Diagrams:** Visualizing process variations. **Error Detection:** Analyzing the root causes of errors and addressing them. SPC helps control errors in production processes and improves product quality, making it a valuable tool for maintaining high standards.

Continuous Improvement Monitoring (CIM) focuses on the ongoing enhancement of processes and increasing organizational efficiency. This approach includes the following key processes: **Performance Assessment:** Evaluating organizational performance to identify existing shortcomings. **Improvement Measures:** Developing strategies to address identified gaps. **Monitoring and Tracking:** Continuously observing processes to detect changes in quality.

CIM allows organizations and manufacturing enterprises to achieve continuous process improvements, thereby enhancing the quality of products or services.

Automated Quality Monitoring Systems. Automating quality monitoring is crucial in collecting and analyzing necessary data for evaluating education quality. Leveraging information and communication technologies (ICT), particularly in centralized monitoring across national higher education institutions, helps reduce workload and optimize time management. For instance, the systems of **attestation** and **state accreditation** illustrate how automation can streamline quality assessments:

- **Attestation:** A two-stage process involving both internal and external evaluations of educational institutions. This assessment covers the institution's activities, students' knowledge levels, staff qualifications, and facilities provided for students.
- **Accreditation:** A formal recognition by a conformity assessment body that grants official authority to perform specific quality assessment tasks. It serves as third-party validation of compliance.

Real-Time Monitoring systems enable the continuous tracking of data and provide updated information about every process. Key benefits include: **Immediate Results Access:** Students' results are directly uploaded into the system, allowing teachers, students, and their parents to access them anytime. **Compliance Monitoring:** Simplifies the monitoring of adherence to educational standards, both nationally and internationally. **Standards Alignment:**

Educational institutions can track their activities to ensure compliance with national or global standards.

Student assessment systems are continuously updated to enhance the evaluation process. These systems offer various features, including:

1. **Online Assessments:** Conducting tests and assessments online, which automates the process and provides quick results.
2. **Individual Progress Tracking:** The system monitors each student's individual learning level, enabling a customized approach to education.

These automated systems not only improve the quality of education but also facilitate data-driven decisions, ultimately contributing to more effective learning environments.

Conclusion. The electronic system for monitoring and assessing educational quality is a digital tool that enables the automated tracking and evaluation of educational processes. Through this system, it becomes easier to monitor the performance of students, teachers, and educational institutions in real-time, as well as to automatically generate evaluation results and reports. The system ensures continuous monitoring of educational quality, promotes transparency, and enhances feedback exchange among all participants. As a result, the educational process is managed more effectively, and compliance with educational standards is improved.

The overall evaluation is shaped based on modern methods of managing educational quality within institutions and the analysis of internal management effectiveness. Continuous reform of the curriculum, ensuring the quality of graduates, and aligning educational, scientific, technical, and technological developments with global standards are among society's key priorities. These efforts are crucial in supporting the deep economic and social reforms currently underway in the country.

In Uzbekistan's national education system, significant efforts have been made in quality assessment and monitoring. Notably, initiatives such as the rating system aimed at fostering healthy competition among general secondary schools, international collaboration, and international assessment programs (PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS) conducted to evaluate students' knowledge are clear examples of these efforts.

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